

**ASSESSMENT CRITERIA OF ORGANIZATIONAL-MANAGEMENT
COMPETENCES OF MASTER'S STUDENTS**

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Abstract. *This thesis analyzes cognitive, motivational, functional, perceptual-reflexive criteria for assessing the organizational and managerial competencies of master's students and describes the levels of formation of organizational and managerial competencies.*

Keywords: *competence, criteria, cognitive, motivational, functional, perceptual-reflexive, organizational and pedagogical characteristics.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada magistratura talabalarining tashkiliy-boshqaruv kompetentsiyalarini baholashning kognitiv, motivatsion, funksional, pertseptiv-refleksiv mezonlari tahlil qilinadi hamda tashkiliy-boshqaruv kompetentsiyalarining shakllanish darajalari tavsiflanadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *kompetentsiya, mezonlar, kognitiv, motivatsion, funksional, pertseptiv-refleksiv, tashkiliy-pedagogik xususiyatlar.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируются когнитивные, мотивационные, функциональные, перцептивно-рефлексивные критерии оценки организационно-управленческих компетенций магистрантов и описываются уровни сформированности организационно-управленческих компетенций.*

Ключевые слова: *компетентность, критерии, когнитивный, мотивационный, функциональный, перцептивно-рефлексивный, организационно-педагогические характеристики.*

The main goal of any higher education institution is to prepare a competitive and in-demand specialist who is able to carry out his professional activities at a high level. One of the main types of future professional activity in the qualification characteristics of a master's student is organizational management. When planning work to develop organizational and managerial competencies of master's students, it is necessary to determine criteria and indicators by which the development of these competencies can be assessed. Their study is important for correctly assessing the development of relevant skills in students and increasing the effectiveness of all work carried out in this direction.

The word "criterion" is derived from the Greek word "criterion" - "measure to evaluate something". "A criterion is a mark, judgment, measure of evaluation by which something is assessed, determined, or classified" [1].

Picture 1. Criterion requirements

At the same time, in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the pedagogical conditions for the formation of the studied competence in master's students, first of all, it is necessary to develop an adequate criterion-evaluation characteristic of the considered competence. In this regard, it is necessary to determine the criteria, levels and indicators of the formation of this phenomenon.

The problem of measuring the results of the formation of organizational-management competence is related to the problem of determining the criteria and levels of its formation. Of course, these criteria are widely revealed by indicators introduced by researchers. It follows from the content of the definition of organizational-management competence of a master's student that this phenomenon should be measured according to the following criteria: cognitive, motivational, functional, perceptive-reflexive. For this, a systematic approach was used, since the selected criteria in turn constitute a systematic formation [5].

The motivational criterion is the understanding and positive evaluation of the goals of formation of organizational and management skills by students; emphasize these skills as an important component of future professional activity; ensure the personal and social importance of providing students with information and developing decision-making skills; value orientation, an attitude of interest in organizational and management activities, that is, it reflects the presence of information and cognitive needs in students. Indicators of this criterion: availability of motivation to acquire skills, cognitive need.

Cognitive criterion - the existence of a system of knowledge about the means and methods of action necessary for the implementation of organizational and management activities. This is expressed by indicators of the completeness and consistency of knowledge about the appropriate means and methods of action. Completeness is the transmission of all important signs and aspects of the process or event under consideration. Consistency is characterized by the preservation of knowledge over time and its repetition under necessary conditions.

Durability is the result of memorizing knowledge and is characterized by the durability factor calculated by the formula.

Next, we take into account the levels of formation of the cognitive component of the studied competence, which is determined in the 100-point rating system with the help of specially designed tasks. If $0 \leq R \leq 100$, the total number of points collected by the student during the current control period is denoted by R.

Formation levels for the considered component are determined as follows: at $R \leq 60$ - adaptive (low) level; At $60 \leq R \leq 80$ - productive (average) level; At $80 \leq R \leq 100$ - reflective-creative (high) level.

The functional criterion of the formation of organizational-management skills reflects the level of mastery of the set of actions that make up the composition of organizational-management skills. It is expressed by the correctness, transmission and speed of movements.

The accuracy of actions is expressed by the accuracy coefficient, which is calculated by the following formula:

$$K_{np} = n/N$$

Here, n is the number of correctly executed actions from those checked, N is the number of checked actions. Researchers (Yu.K.Babansky, V.P.Bespalko) developed rating scales and indicated three levels of accuracy: low, medium, high. The limits of the accuracy coefficient values are given in table 1.

**Table 1.
Accuracy factor threshold**

Levels	Accuracy coefficient value
low	$K_{np} < 0,7$
medium	$0,7 \leq K_{np} \leq 0,85$
high	$K_{np} > 0,85$

Transfer reflects the ability to apply the formed skills in changed conditions, taking into account the peculiarities of new conditions. The speed of performance of the skill in question is the speed of performance of the operations that make up the structure of the skill.

The perceptive-reflexive criterion shows that the subject of organizational-management activity has three types of sensitivity:

a) sense of the object - the leader's sensitivity to how the objects of reality find a response in the subordinates, how the interests and needs of the subordinates correspond to the demands placed on them;

b) a sense of proportionality and tact - a special sensitivity to the degree of changes in the personality and activity of subordinates under the influence of various means of management influence, with what signs they can be evaluated, whether they are positive or negative;

c) sense of involvement - characterized by the leader's sensitivity to shortcomings in his work, his criticality and responsibility for the work of the team.

Indicators of this criterion are the ability to understand the inner world of another person with self-reflection, the adequacy of self-esteem, the ability to take responsibility. The established system of criteria for the formation of organizational-management competencies among students and their diagnostic methods are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Table of criteria for formation of organizational-management competencies in master's students

Criteria	Indicators of their manifestation	Diagnostic methods
<i>Motivational</i>	Availability of motivation, cognitive need to acquire organizational-management skills	Questions, interviews, individual conversations, observations, sociometry
	The completeness and strength of knowledge about	The completeness and strength of knowledge about

<i>Cognitive</i>	the means and methods of action necessary for the implementation of organizational and management activities	the means and methods of action necessary for the implementation of organizational and management activities
<i>Functional</i>	Correctness, transmission, speed of performing a set of actions on data search (collection), reception and storage; information processing (analysis, systematization, generalization, etc.), information encoding (verbal, figurative); solving problems of different levels of cognitive accuracy (requiring simple mental operations with data, requiring complex mental operations with data, requiring data reporting, requiring creative thinking)	Methods of determining the level of formation of the main methods of mental activity, the level of development of logical abilities; perform tasks that require complex mental operations; assignments for practical application; problematic tasks; tasks of applying one's observations (emotionally based) and one's judgments (rationally based); operations research application tasks; decoration, filling out self-assessment cards; presentation of reports, creative projects, multimedia presentations
<i>Perceptive-reflexive</i>	The ability to understand the inner world of another person with self-reflection, the adequacy of self-esteem, the ability to take responsibility	Analysis of answers and self-analysis in training; activity monitoring; interviewing; sociometry; analysis of communication situations; participate in discussions; group work; self-assessment cards

The established criteria and levels of formation of organizational and managerial competencies make it possible not only to obtain information about the effectiveness of the educational process aimed at developing the skills in question, to assess the formation of the necessary skills at a certain stage of specialist training, but also to monitor the dynamics of the formation of students as organizational and managerial subjects.

The criteria for evaluating the levels of formation of organizational-management competencies of master's students may include the following indicators:

1. To know the basic principles of organization management, its structure and operation.
2. Ability to analyze information and make decisions based on data analysis.
3. Project and team management skills, including planning, coordination and control.
4. The ability to develop strategies and tactics to achieve your goals.
5. Communication and persuasive skills, including the ability to work with people, persuade and motivate them.

6. Ability to work in conditions of uncertainty and change, adapt to new conditions and quickly respond to changes.

Evaluation criteria and levels of formation of master's students' organizational and management competencies are important aspects for universities and educational institutions to evaluate the skills and capabilities of students in these areas. Organizational-management competencies play a decisive role in the success of people in the workplace and help organizations work effectively. Therefore, the assessment and development of these competencies in graduate students is essential for their future career prospects.

When it comes to assessing organizational-management competencies, it is important to define clear criteria that measure the required skills and abilities. These criteria must match the competencies expected in the business world and reflect the ever-changing demands of the labor market. Some commonly used assessment criteria for organizational-management competencies include:

1. Communication Skills: this criterion assesses the student's ability to effectively communicate information, ideas, and instructions to others through a variety of means, including verbal, written, and nonverbal communication.

2. Leadership Skills: this criterion assesses the student's ability to direct and motivate a team to achieve common goals, make decisions, delegate tasks, and resolve conflicts.

3. Problem Solving Skills: this criterion examines a student's ability to identify, analyze, and solve complex problems by applying critical thinking, logical reasoning, and creativity.

4. Decision-Making Skills: this criterion assesses the student's ability to make timely and effective decisions based on available information, consider alternatives, and evaluate potential risks and outcomes.

5. Time Management and Organization: this criterion assesses the student's ability to prioritize tasks, manage resources effectively, meet deadlines, and take a systematic approach to work.

6. Adaptability: this criterion assesses the student's ability to adapt to changes, work effectively in a dynamic environment, and absorb new ideas and technologies.

Once the assessment criteria are established, it is important to identify the different levels of formation for each competency. These levels help assess the success and development of master's students in acquiring and mastering organizational-management competencies. In general, the levels of formation can be classified as follows [9]:

1. Lower Level: At this level, students have a basic understanding of organizational-management competencies, but not much practical application. They need guidance and support to develop their skills.

2. Intermediate level: At this level, students demonstrate an average level of competence in the application of organizational-management skills. They can perform tasks with minimal supervision and have had some experience in realistic scenarios.

3. Advanced level: At this level, students acquire advanced skills and organizational-management competencies. They can independently solve complex tasks, provide leadership and make informed decisions.

4. Expert level: This level represents exceptional skills and experience. Students at this level have a broad understanding of organizational-management competencies, are able to effectively manage diverse teams, and have advanced analytical and strategic thinking skills.

By assessing the organizational and management skills of master’s students based on these criteria and levels of formation, educational institutions can provide targeted feedback and guidance to help students and improve their skills. This assessment process ensures that students are well prepared for the challenges of the professional world and equips them with the necessary competencies to succeed in management and leadership roles.

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